

Morphological Forms and Metaphorical Dynamics of Banana Lexicon in Balinese Language: An Ecolinguistics Study

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ABSTRACT: This paper aims at (1) describing and analyzing the morphological forms of the Balinese lexicon on bananas, (2) analyzing the categories' and revealing their dynamics, and (3) describing metaphors related to bananas and revealing their dynamics. Structural linguistic and Ecolinguistics theories proposed by Haugen are used for the analysis which refer to the three objectives. The data was collected through interview and observation methods; qualitative method was applied on the analysis of banana forms, the categories, as well as its metaphors. The dynamics of the lexicon were analyzed based on quantitative methods and descriptive-analytic technique. The results of the analysis were presented by using formal and informal methods completed with inductive and deductive techniques. The results of the analysis show (1) the morphological forms of the banana lexicon in Balinese are base forms (free morphemes), derived forms (affixed, reduplications, compound words, and phrasal forms); (2) the vocabulary of the banana lexicon consists of categories such as: 16 nouns, 16 numbers, 21 verbs, and 25 adjectives. Traditionally there are 18 types of bananas. In relation to the dynamics of banana lexicon there are found 4 new names of bananas. The knowledge of the banana's terms shows a decrease from generation to generation. This is evidenced by the results of the questionnaires for the older generation to adults, for the adolescents both the terms, the category of bananas and the knowledge of the Balinese metaphor for bananas.

KEYWORDS: dynamic, form, lexicon, Balinese

I. INTRODUCTION

Changes in language can occur both towards development and towards extinction. Based on the observations, there are several new lexicons that appear in a language, nevertheless there are also lexicons that are extinct. The dynamics of the lexicon can represent changes in the environment in which a language is used. The evidence that environmental changes can affect the dynamics of the lexicon of a language that can be exemplified as follows: community groups who work as farmers and cultivators about fifty years ago only knew a set of lexicons of old cultivated plants, traditional tillage tools, and manure. Nowadays, lexicons among others, such as pesticides, hybrids, tractors, organic/non-organic fertilizers are in use. In addition, the intensification and intensification in plantations and agriculture have caused many ancient lexicons related to agriculture and traditional cultivation to be displaced and eventually extinct (Mbete et al. 2009:99). In other words, language changes can occur because of changes in the environment, both in the natural environment and in the social environment, which is marked by the loss of certain lexicons that represent the previous natural environment.

In addition to the extinction of several lexicons, language changes (in a positive or developing direction) are marked by the emergence of lexicons, both those formed through a borrowing process, speaker innovations through a compounding process, or through mixing parts of a lexicon with other elements from another lexicon (Halliday as cited in Fill and Muehlhauser, ed.: 2001).

Sosiowati, et.al (2019) reports a study on the vitality of the fishing lexicon in Loloan Malay. The study was aimed at finding the nature and pattern of domain change, its inter- generational transmission, and its significance for overall ethnolinguistic vitality. The data were collected from a representative group of fishermen through tests that were complemented by interviews. A simple quantitative analysis was under- taken to discover patterns of change, and the ethnographic method was also used to augment the analysis. This study contributes to sociolinguistic research on language vitality, contact-induced change, and the endangerment of minority languages. The findings reveal a surprising paradox. Although it is still considered to have high

cultural importance, the fishing domain is critically endangered. It is argued that the low vitality of the fishing domain does not affect the vitality of the Loloan Malay language in general. The reason is that the linguistic ideology that underpins the group identity of Loloan Malay at the macro-societal level is not tied to fishing, but rather, to religion. Particularly discusses the complexity of the variables involved in domain change, particularly the extra-linguistic factors that contribute to the changes in the fishing domain due to modern socio-economic and technological progress.

Research on the vitality of the Balinese lexicons on Prapen and Memande in Denpasar has also been done by Indrawati and Puspani (2022). It was aimed at finding the nature and form of the domain change, its intergeneration transference, and its implication for comprehensive ethnolinguistic vitality. The data were taken from a distinctive group of blacksmiths (Pande) in Denpasar City, Bali Province, through interviews and questionnaires. The results showed that even though it is acknowledged to have high cultural significance, the Prapen and Memande lexicons are at the level of unsafe. It is appealed that the negative vitality of the Prapen and Memande lexicons did not affect the vitality of the overall Balinese language. The linguistic ideology that reinforced the group identity of Pande (the Black Smiths) at the huge community level is not linked to Memande, yet relatively to the belief and identity.

Based on the above phenomena, it is undeniable that this phenomenon is unlikely to occur in the Balinese language. Balinese language is one of the regional languages in the archipelago used as a symbol of identity, supporting culture, as a means of communication among speakers of Balinese. One of the phenomena is the dynamics of Balinese lexicon on bananas.

Banana is a very important fruit for human life, especially in the Hindu community in Bali and outside Bali. In the meantime, it is the most important fruit for preparing offerings for Balinese Hindu. Regarding the lexicon on bananas, it varies in numbers from one language to another language. Concerning the types of bananas, the lexicons related to bananas differ in the form of the category and the names of the banana. Likewise, from its function, bananas are very important for the Balinese people not only as an ingredient to fulfill their vitamin needs, but more than that, the function of bananas in Balinese society for religious purposes is very high.

By means of the advances in agricultural technology on one hand, the movement of globalization through free trade causes goods (including bananas) to enter freely to increase the knowledge of the Balinese people about bananas terms. On the other hand, there are types of bananas that are reducing and even disappearing in certain areas. This condition allows several banana lexicons and its supporting elements to become extinct. To track the extinct lexicons of bananas, we attempt to record new lexicons to answer three problems discussed in this opportunity, namely (1) what are the morphological forms of the banana lexicon in Balinese? (2) how are the dynamics of the lexicon of the Balinese language? (3) What are the metaphors related to bananas and how their dynamics are.

II. THEORY, METHOD, AND DATA SOURCE

To solve the problems regarding the dynamics of banana lexicons, Eco linguistic theory is applied and supported with structural linguistic theory to discuss the forms of the Balinese language lexicon. Eco linguistic theory was first introduced by Gumperz (1962). (Gumperz as cited in Sarmi 2015: 34) suggests the idea of ecolinguistics as the interaction between language and its environment through language speakers. This shows that it is because the speakers of the language develop (a new lexicon appears), survive (the existing lexicons are still used), shift (the replacement of certain lexicons with other lexicons), or become extinct (the disappearance of certain lexicons).

Gumperz's idea was later strengthened by Haugen (in Dil, 1972: 325-329) who states that the environment of a language is speakers of language which can take the form of social and cultural backgrounds. In addition, language through its lexicon also represents its physical environment, such as rivers, lakes, mountains, rice fields, and so forth. The facts show that the natural environment changes, the language used by speakers also changes over time. Likewise, the lexicon of bananas in Balinese must have experienced changes as mentioned by Gumperz and Haugen. The structural theory used is the theory of de Saussure (1916) with its dichotomies that are appropriate to this problem.

The methods applied in providing data were the direct observation and interview methods (Sudaryanto, 1988: 2-9). The direct observation method was applied by listening to Balinese speakers while they are speaking and taking notes on vocabulary related to bananas. In addition, the initial data was also patterned in the Balinese Indonesian dictionary (to determine the initial data used as a guide for examining the dynamics of the lexicon. To crosscheck the dynamics of Balinese lexicons on bananas,

interview method was applied by interviewing all the informants. In the data analysis, a qualitative method was used accompanied by descriptive-analytic techniques to analyze the forms of Balinese banana lexicon and descriptions of banana names, as well as the categories of the Balinese banana lexicon. The dynamics of the Balinese lexicons on banana were analyzed using quantitative method since it required numbers. To present the results of the analysis, a formal method was used, specifically presentation using graphic tables. In addition, an informal method was used, that is the presentation by using words assisted with inductive and deductive presentation techniques. Sources of data for a guide to viewing dynamics and linguistic forms were taken from Balinese speakers who use Balinese as their mother tongue and the Balinese Indonesian Dictionary. However, for the analysis of dynamics the lexicon was taken from the Balinese speakers who use Balinese as their mother tongue in three generations, that is the older generation aged 46-65 years, the adult generation aged 26-45 years, and the youth generation aged 17-25 years. Each generation was taken by 100 people from various regions in Bali. Consequently, there were 300 informants for the dynamics of the lexicon.

III. DISCUSSIONS

Regarding the problem, three things are discussed specifically, the forms of the Balinese lexicon on banana, their categories and dynamics; and metaphors related to bananas and their dynamics. Each problem is described below in detail.

3.1 The Balinese Lexicon on Bananas can be in the base forms and derived ones.

The forms described below are the base form. According to Ramlan (1985: 45) base forms are units, both single and complex, which form the basis for larger units. Chaer (2012: 159) states that the basic form is a form that is the basis of a morphological process. Further information and examples are described in detail in table 1 below.

Table 1: The Balinese Lexicons on Banana in the Base Forms

No.	Base Forms	Meaning
1.	<i>Biyu /biu/</i>	banana
2.	<i>Don /don/</i>	leaf
3.	<i>Kraras /kraras/</i>	dry banana leaf
4.	<i>Gadang /gadang/</i>	green
5.	<i>Kuning /kuning/</i>	yellow
6.	<i>Gede /gæde/</i>	big
7.	<i>Cenik /cənik/</i>	small
8.	<i>Pusuh /pusuh/</i>	banana flower
9.	<i>Bah /bah/</i>	fell off
10.	<i>Tegeh /təgəh/</i>	high

Data (1-10) in table 1 above are named base forms since they are not affixed and they are in the forms of free morphemes. Additionally, they cannot be split into smaller units. That is the reason they are sometimes termed single forms.

3.2 The Balinese Lexicon on Banana in the Derived Forms

Kridalaksana (1996) states derived forms are lexicons that have undertaken morphological processes in the form of affixation, reduplication, and compound. The lexicons on bananas that undergo morphological processes can be in the forms of affixed words, reduplication, and compound words. A more detailed description is as follows:

The Balinese Lexicons of Banana with Affixations.

The Balinese Lexicons of Banana with affixations consist of the base forms affixed with prefixes, infixes, and suffixes as can be seen in the following table.

Table 2: The Balinese Lexicon on Banana in the Derived Forms

No.	Morphological process	Derived forms	Meaning
1	<i>N – tugel</i>	<i>nugel /nugel/</i>	to cut
2	<i>N- sepeg</i>	<i>nyepeg</i>	to cut down trees
3	<i>N-bambang-ang</i>	<i>mambangang</i>	to make a hole
4	<i>N -bah-ang</i>	<i>ngebahang</i>	to lay down
5	<i>N- Sekeb</i>	<i>nyekeb</i>	the process of becoming ripe
6	<i>a-tugel</i>	<i>atugel</i>	one piece
7	<i>a-iyis</i>	<i>aiyis</i>	a slice
8	<i>Gede-ang</i>	<i>gedenang</i>	enlarge
9	<i>Cenik-ang</i>	<i>cenikang</i>	make smaller
10	<i>Tegeh-ang</i>	<i>tegehang</i>	make higher
11	<i>Ma-pusuh</i>	<i>mapusuh</i>	having bud
12	<i>Ma-don</i>	<i>medon</i>	having leaf
13	<i>Sekeb-a</i>	<i>sekeba</i>	being processed to make the bananas ripe
14	<i>Petek-in</i>	<i>petekin</i>	count repeatedly
15	<i>Lepit-in</i>	<i>lepitin</i>	fold repeatedly

Data (1,2, and 5) on table 2 shows that prefix N- or nasal is attached to the base forms of verbal categories, *tugel*, *sepeg*, and *sekeb* to become *nugel*, *nyepeg*, and *nyekeb*. Data (3 and 4) show that *bambang* (noun) and *bah* (intransitive verb) are suffixed by causative derivational suffix *-ang* to become *mambangang* and *ngebahang*. Then they are prefixed with prefix *ma-* to become *mambangang* and *ngebahang*. Data (6 and 7) show that prefix *a-* is attached to the base *tugel* and *iyis* to become *atugel* and *aiyis*. Data (8-10) shows that causative derivational suffix *-ang* is attached to the adjectives *gede*, *cenik*, and *tegeh* to become causative verbs, *gedenang*, *cenikang*, and *tegehang*. Data 11 and 12, the nouns *pusuh* and *don* are prefixed by *ma-* to become intransitive verbs *mapusuh* and *madon*. Data (13), the verb *sekeb* is suffixed with passive marker *-a* to become *sekeba*. Data 14 and 15 show that prefix *-in* is attached to the verb base *petek* and *lepit* to become *petekin* and *lepitin* with the meaning repeated actions.

3.3 The Balinese Lexicon of Banana in Compound Word Forms

Compound words are words that are formed by combining two words/precategories as their constituent components (Verhaar, 2012: 154). The Balinese lexicon of banana can be in compound word forms such as shown in table 3.

Table 3: The Balinese Lexicon of Banana in Compound Word Forms

No	Compound words	Morphological process	Meaning
1.	<i>Biyu kayu</i>	<i>biyu</i> “banana”+ <i>kayu</i> ” wood”	certain type of banana
2.	<i>Biyu susu</i>	<i>biyu</i> “banana”+ <i>susu</i> ‘milk’	certain type of banana
3.	<i>Biyu mas</i>	<i>biyu</i> “banana”+ <i>mas</i> ‘gold’	certain type of banana
4.	<i>Kuning mrengpeng</i>	<i>Kuning</i> ‘yellow’ + <i>mrengpeng</i> ‘bright’ (unique morpheme)	bright yellow
5.	<i>Nguda pelek</i>	<i>Nguda</i> ‘young’ + <i>pelek</i> ‘very’	very young

The compound forms of Balinese lexicons on banana consist of noun base and noun base as can be seen in data (1-3); and adjective and intensifier base as in data (4 and 5).

Word categories on the Balinese Lexicon on Banana and their Dynamics.

Before discussing the dynamics of banana lexicon in Balinese, the categories and names of bananas are discussed because they are used as guidance to find out how the dynamics of banana lexicon is up to the present time. On this occasion the categories discussed are nouns, numerals, verbs, and adjectives. The description is presented on table 4 below:

Table 4: The word or phrasal category of the Balinese Lexicons on Bananas

No	Noun	No.	Quantifier	No.	Adjective	No.	Verb
1.	<i>Plosor biu</i> 'young leaf of banana'	1	<i>Asisir</i> 'a slice of'	1	<i>Nguda pelek</i> 'very young'	1	<i>Mangbangang</i> 'make a hole'
2.	<i>Don biu</i>	2	<i>Atugel</i> 'a piece of'	2	<i>Nguda</i> 'young'	2	<i>Mamula</i> 'to plant'
3.	<i>Keraras</i> 'dry banana leaf'.	3	<i>Atugel</i> 'a piece of'	3	<i>Empet ati</i> 'very young'	3	<i>Najuk</i> 'plant'
4.	<i>Papah biu</i> 'banana fronds'	4	<i>Abulih</i> 'quantifier specificatin for one banana'	4	<i>Wayah</i> 'ripe'	4	<i>Mulungin</i> 'loosen the soil around using a hoe'
5.	<i>Pusuh</i> 'bud'	5	<i>Abesik</i> 'one'	5	<i>Gadang</i> 'green'	5	<i>Nglemekin</i> 'fertilizing'
6.	<i>Bungan pusuh</i> 'flower inside the bud'	6	<i>Aijas</i> 'a hand of'	6	<i>Nasak</i> 'ripe'	6	<i>Musuhin</i> 'to cut the bud off'
7.	<i>Klopak pusuh</i> 'bud petals'	7	<i>Abaa</i> 'a hand of'	7	<i>Gading</i> 'yellowish'	7	<i>Mapahin</i> 'the strategy to cut'
8.	<i>Gedebong</i> 'bananas trunk'	8	<i>Aijeng</i> 'a bunch'	8	<i>Kuning</i> 'yellow'	8	<i>Nyeppeg</i> 'to cut'
9.	<i>Klopak gedebong</i> 'trunk petals'	9	<i>Apuun</i> 'one tree'	9	<i>Belek</i> 'mushy'	9	<i>Ngangget</i> 'to cut'
10.	<i>Atin gedebong</i> 'the inside of the trunk'	10	<i>Auwit</i> 'one group'	10	<i>Lodoh,</i> 'very soggy'	10	<i>Ngalap</i> 'to pick'
11.	<i>Bungkil biu</i> 'the root part of the bananas'	11	<i>Alingseh</i> 'a group of'	11	<i>Berek</i> 'rotten'	11	<i>Ngijasin</i> 'to put into one hand'
12.	<i>Akah biu</i> 'banana's root'	12	<i>Asaih</i> 'one hectare'	12	<i>Beler selem</i> 'rotten and black in colour'	12	<i>Nyemuhin</i> 'to dry'
13.	<i>Kulit biu</i> 'banana's skin'	13	<i>Alepit</i> 'one-fold'	13	<i>Leh burik</i> 'with freckles'	13	<i>Nyekeb</i> 'the process of riping'
14.	<i>Isi pisang</i> 'the flesh'	14	<i>Akebesan</i> 'a piece of'	14	<i>Balangan</i> 'ripe not properly'	14	<i>Ngungkabang</i> 'to open'
15.	<i>Serat</i> 'fiber'	15	<i>Abidang</i> 'a larger piece'	15	<i>Sepet</i> 'bitter'	15	<i>Masriak</i> 'getting ripe at once'
16.	<i>Tali kupas</i> 'peel rope'	16	<i>Apapah</i> 'a piece of'	16	<i>Manis</i> 'sweet'	16	<i>Mbud</i> 'new flower buds grow'
				17	<i>Masem-masemmanis</i> 'sour sweet'	17	<i>Ngebah</i> 'to cut down'
				18	<i>Nyanggal</i> 'solid'	18	<i>Melut</i> 'to peel'
				19	<i>Layu</i> 'withered'	19	<i>Nyepih</i> 'to classify'
				21	<i>Matah</i> 'raw'	20	<i>Nanem</i> 'to plant'

				21	<i>Bonyok</i> 'over ripe'		
				22	<i>Blantahan</i> 'not well riped'		
				23	<i>Tluhtuhan</i> 'ripe but part of skin colour is green'		

There are 16 nouns, 16 quantifiers, 23 adjectives, and 20 verbs found related to the banana lexicons.

The Balinese terms on bananas

Based on the observations, the traditional terms of bananas are (1) *biyu kayu*; (2) *biu raja*; (3) *biyu susu*; (4) *biyu gadang*; (5) *biyu lumut*; (6) *biu mas*; (7) *biu bawe*; (8) *biu dang saba*; (9) *biyu tabah*; (10) *biyu temaga*; (11) *biyu kapal*; (12) *biu dak nangka*; (13) *biyu batu*; (14) *biyu keladi*; (15) *biu ketip tulang*; (16) *biu ketip letung*; (17) *biu alas*; (18) *biu buluh*. The names of banana in recent development are: *biu kalpendis*, *biu pecah seribu*, *biu sangket*, and *biu candi*.

The Dynamics of the Balinese Lexicons on Banana

To find out the dynamics of banana lexicon in Balinese, a lexicon related to the name of bananas and a category of lexicon related to bananas, there were questionnaires which are distributed to 300 Balinese speakers within three age groups, they are: young (age 15-25), adults (age 26-45), old (46-65) years, with 100 respondents for each group. There are four alternative answers for questions on the knowledge of the bananas' name and the noun category namely, A = acknowledged, and there are lots of them remain; B = acknowledged, but it is rare; C = acknowledged, but already extinct; D = do not acknowledge at all. For questions measuring understanding of the categories of verbs, quantifiers, adjectives, and metaphors, 4 alternative answers were also given, namely A = acknowledged, and are still in use, B = acknowledged, and are rarely used, C = acknowledged, is never used, D = do not acknowledge at all. Based on these criteria, the dynamic results of the knowledge of the lexicon on bananas are presented in the following graph.

Graphic 1: The Dynamics of the Balinese Lexicons on Banana

The bananas and their names still exist but the amount depends on the varieties. Nevertheless, based on the results of the observations in graph 1, it is stated that the level of knowledge on the names of bananas can be described as follows: the average for answer A =acknowledged, and there are lots of them remain: the percentage of knowledge for each group of respondents are as

follows: old respondents 47.14%, adults 45.59%, and young 40.73%. Those who answered B= acknowledged, but it is rare: old 22.50%, adults 15.68%, and young 14.27%. Those who answered C = acknowledged, but already extinct: older people 5.14%, adults 3.68%, and teenagers 4.82%; those who answered D = do not acknowledge at all: old 25.27%, adults 35.05%, and teenagers 40.18%.

The knowledge of the banana terms in Bali is strongly influenced by the taste and its function in fulfilling the needs for the ceremony. This is evidenced by the acknowledge of the name of *Biu Susu*, choice A as the answer is very high, namely: 99% young, 99% adults, and 90% old. It shows that young people also know the name of the banana well (similarly, the percentage of *biu raja* who answered A is also high). Unlike the case with *biu temaga*, the very low number of answering A, namely young 6%, adults 17%, and old 9%, since this type of banana tastes bad, specifically sour, so it is not widely cultivated, but they still exist. This type of banana is still planted because of its red colour and it has an important function in Hinduism to fulfill the needs of offerings (similarly, *biu alas* cannot be eaten but it is important to meet the needs of the offerings). The other types of bananas with the percentage of answers were quite low for young adults, and old respondents were *biu mas*, *biu bawean*, and *biyu taro*. These banana names are also very important and have their own functions in offerings. It is different from *biu kayu*, which has an important function and good taste, those who answered A were also 70% young, 75% adults, and 69% old.

Graphic 2: Percentage of knowledge of the Balinese Lexicons on bananas in nominal category.

Table 2 shows that the knowledge of the noun category of banana are as follows: the average answer, A = acknowledged, and are still in use: old 93.75%, adults 94.94%, and young group 80.19 ; those who answered B= acknowledged, but it is rare: old 4.81%, adults 3.94%, young 9.31%; for those who answered C=acknowledged, but it is rare: older people 0.5%, adults 0.06%, and young 2.12%; those who answered D = do not acknowledge at all: old 0.94%, adults 1.06 and young 8.38%.

The knowledge of noun categories related to bananas is still very good because only a small percentage of respondents who answer D. The old average knowledge is 0.94%, adults 1.06% and young 8.38%. Of the 16 categories of nouns, the one that was most unknown to the younger generation (28 people) was *tali kupas* 'a rope made from dried banana tree petals.' This makes sense because nowadays ropes have been replaced by plastic ropes in villages. Next is the *pelosor biu* 'young banana leaf that is just growing' unknown to as many as 20 teenagers. Next, 12 people did not know about *bungkil biu* 'the bottom of banana tree', and 11 people did not *atin gedebong* 'the inside part of banana trunk '. Meanwhile, the others were not known by the younger

generation, it is below ten respondents. While the adult and older generations, there are only one, two, and a maximum of five, who do not know one of the nouns namely the name of *serat* 'fiber.'

Graphic 3: Percentage on the knowledge of quantifiers related to banana.

Graphic 3 shows an understanding of the number categories associated with bananas at the young, adult, and old levels. The category of numbers related to bananas still exists and is used in villages and areas with lots of banana trees because these numbers have collocations with bananas. Graphic 3 shows that there is a significant decrease in the understanding of quantifiers related to bananas. The average answers A = acknowledged, and are still in use: old, 81.83 %, adults 78.65 %, and young 66.77%; those who answered B= acknowledged, but it is rare: old, 7.53%, adults 7.76%, young 11.47%; for those who answered C = acknowledged, but it is rare: old 1.76%, adults 3.59%, and young, 2.94%; those who answered D =do not acknowledge at all: old, 8.88%, adults, 10%, and young, 18.82%.

Based on graphic 3, the lexicon *asaih* 'one hectare' is mostly unknown; the older generation (31 respondents), adults (39 respondents) and young (50 respondents); next *auwit* 'one tree' is unknown to the older generation (42 respondents), adult (39 respondents), and young (46respondents); then, the word *abaa* 'a bunch of', are not known by the older generation (43respondents), adults (39respondents), and young (30respondents). Smaller amount of young and adult group does not know about it compared to the older generation. Furthermore, the lexicon *alepit* 'one leaf fold' is unknown to 50 young, 10 adults, and 2 old groups. The knowledge of this word has considerably decreased because the use of leaves has also now been replaced by paper, therefore they are no longer familiar with the lexicon. The other words are still well acknowledged, only below 20 respondents do not know them. Words that are starting to decrease in understanding for the younger generation, especially in urban areas because they are rarely involved with these quantifiers. For speakers in rural areas, they still know them well.

Graphic 4: Percentage of knowledge on verbal category related to banana

Graphic 4 shows the understanding of the categories of verbs related to bananas at the young, adult, and old levels. The category of verbs related to bananas still exists and is used in villages and cities where there are banana trees. It shows a decrease in understanding of verbs. For the level of understanding of the lexicon category of verbs, the average answer A = acknowledged, and are still in use: old 85.48 %, adults 86.71 %, and young 70.48; those who answered B = acknowledged, but it is rare: old group, 8.48 %; adults 5.24 %; young, 8.29 %; for those who answered C = acknowledged, but it is rare: old group, 2.10 %, adults 1.62 %, and young, 4.05 %; those who answered D = do not acknowledge at all: old, 3.94 %, adults, 6.43 %, and young, 17.18 %.

Of the 21 lexicons related to bananas listed in graphic 4, 8 lexicons are not known by more than 20 respondents (20%). The lexicon most unknown to young group (45 respondents), adults (25 respondents), and old (11 respondents) is *mangabangang* 'making holes'; *najuk* 'planting' 40 young group, 7 adults, and 8 old; *nnglemekin* 'giving fertilizer' was unknown to 38 young, 21 adults, and 3 old. These three words are not well known because the word *najuk* has another form, namely *nanem* 'planting' which is just unknown to 3 young respondents, while the word *nnglemekin* for young respondents is influenced by the Indonesian language, *ngarabuk* 'to give fertilizer'. The root word comes from the Indonesian language with prefix {N-} with the allomorph /ng-/.

Graphic 5: Percentage of knowledge on adjectival category related to banana

Graphic 5 shows the understanding of the adjective categories related to bananas at the young, adult, and old levels. Based on the observations in graphic 5, there is a significant decrease in understanding because for the level of understanding of the lexicon of the banana noun category, the average answer is A = acknowledged, and are still in use: old group, 82.56 %, adults 82.4 %, and young 71.48 % ; those who answered B = acknowledged, but it is rare: old 7.28 %, adults 5.16 %, young, 7.84%; for those who answered C = acknowledged, but it is rare: old 2.68 %, adults 2.2 %, and young 4.24 %; who answered D = do not acknowledge at all: old 7.48 %, adults 10.24 %, and young, 16.44%

The understanding of the adjective lexicon is still high, although there are those who answer D = do not acknowledge at all. Of the 25 adjectives in the graphic, the lexicon that is most unknown is the lexicon of *biu tlutuhan* 'bad condition of bananas': old, 39 respondents, adults, 45 and young, 60; *empetati* 'banana with insides are new and full of tissue but not yet ripe' was not known by: old, 36; adults, 54; and young, 61; *nguda plek* 'very young' is unknown by: old, 25; adults, 36; and young, 53; and *balangan* lexicon 'bananas with a slightly firm flesh' is unknown to: old, 33 ; adults, 37; and young, 26. Those lexicons are not familiar because they are unique and rarely available or needed by common speakers. The lexicons are only used by speakers who are involved in theology.

Metaphors related to the Balinese lexicons on banana and their dynamics

This study found four metaphors related to the Balinese lexicons on banana; they are

- | | | | |
|----------------------------------|-------|---------|--------------|
| Cara | anake | negakin | gedebong |
| like | one | sits on | banana trunk |
| Like one sitting on banana trunk | | | |

This metaphor is addressed to someone who feels guilty because of doing something wrong to others.

- | | | | |
|------------------------------------|-----|-------|------------|
| Ngudiang | Cai | madon | biyu tuh |
| why | You | leaf | banana dry |
| Why do you like dry banana leaves? | | | |

Dry banana leaf is called *kraras* in Balinese. *Kraras /kraras/* is closely related to the word *reres /rəras/, ngereres /ŋərərəs/* means getting weaker. Therefore, this metaphor is addressed to someone who looks unwell.

3 *Bikas* *nyaine* *madon* *biyu tuh*
 behaviour You Leaf dry banana
 You are always fashionable.

Similar to data 2, this metaphor also contains *don biyu tuh* ‘dry banana leaf’ which referred to as *kraras /kraras/*. However, in this context *kraras /kraras/* is associated with the word *raras /raras/* which means fashionable. This metaphor is addressed to a woman who is fashionable.

4 *Idupne* *cara* *uni* *biyu*
 His life like life banana
 His life is like the life of banana

Uni biyu equals to banana’s life. After having fruit then it dies. If life is compared to banana’s life, it means that the life is short. It is addressed to someone who has a short life.

The dynamics on the metaphors related to the Balinese Lexicons on Banana

The percentage of knowledge on the metaphors related to the Balinese Lexicons is presented in Graphic 6.

Graphic 6: Percentage of knowledge on the metaphors related to the Balinese Lexicons on Banana

Graphic 6 shows the knowledge of metaphors related to bananas in the young, adult, and older generations. As stated above, there are four metaphors related to bananas in Balinese. Traditionally banana metaphor was often used, but nowadays, because of the influence of the Indonesian language this has begun to be forgotten. Based on graphic 6, it is known that there is a decrease in the understanding of metaphors, even though the older generation also has an average understanding on these metaphors below 50%. Consequently, on the average, those who answered A = acknowledged, and are still in use: old group 47.75%, adults 48%, and young 34.75 %; those who answered B = acknowledged, but it is rare: older group achieves 24.25%, adults 22.5%, young 18.5 %; for those who answered C = acknowledged, but it is rare: older group 8.5%, adult 4.75%, and young 8%; who answered D = do not acknowledge at all: old 19.5%, adults 24.75%, and young 38.75 %.

Of the four existing metaphors, the one most acknowledged is the metaphor ‘*Cara anake negakin gedebong*’. It is like someone who feels guilty because of doing something wrong to others.’ The knowledge for this metaphor is: who answered A=acknowledged, and are still in use: old group 81%, adults 67%, and young 55%; second metaphor no3 *Bikas nyaine madon biyu tuh (raras)* ‘You are always fashionable’ is answered A=acknowledged, and are still in use by the older generation 46%, adults 39%, and young 28%; metaphor no2 *Ngudiang cai madon biyu tuh (ngreres)* “Why are you like a sick person who gets worse and worse”, who answered A=acknowledged, and are still in use, the highest is the adult generation, 51% , old 39%, and young 34%. It seems that the last metaphor is the least understood and most people do not know it is a metaphor; metaphor no. 4 *idupne cara uni biyu* ‘Like a woman who died after giving a birth to a baby’. The respondents who answered D= do not know or do not know at all: old, 32%; adults, 36%; and young group, 51%.

Even though all lexicons of bananas have decreased in their understanding and some even answered D = do not know or do not know at all, currently the revitalization of the use and understanding of the Balinese language has begun to be encouraged in various ways with the purpose and expectation that more understanding will be increased in all fields in the future.

Graphic 7: Dynamics of Average Understanding on the Banana Lexicon

Overall, the dynamics of banana lexicon in Balinese can be seen on graph 7. Based on graph 7, it can be seen that the average understanding on banana lexicon in the older generation who answered A= acknowledged, and are still in use: 73,08%, who answered B= acknowledged, but it is rare: 12,47%, who answered C = acknowledged, but it is rare: 3,44%, and those who answered D = do not acknowledge at all: 10,99%.

For adult generation, who answered A = acknowledged, and are still in use: 72,71%, who answered B = acknowledged, but it is rare : 10,04%, who answered C = acknowledged, but it is rare : 2,65%, and who answered D: 14,58%. For young generation, who answered A: 60,73%, who answered B = acknowledged, but it is rare: 11,62, who answered C: 4,36%, and those who answered D = do not acknowledge at all: 23,29%. Based on the average percentage understanding banana lexicon, it was found that those who answered A= acknowledged, and are still in use is from old generation to adults and to generations old it decreased; while those who answered D = do not acknowledge at all, from old generation to adult generation, and to young generations in which the percentage becomes higher or bigger. That means there is reduction in understanding banana lexicon in Balinese language in Balinese from old generation to adults and to young generation.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the discussion, it could be concluded that; (1) the forms of the lexicon were in basic forms (both free and bound/pre-categorized); Derivative forms or in the forms of affixed words, reduplications, and compound words. (2) the categories of banana lexicons are nouns with a total number of 16; numbers, 16; verbs, 21; and adjectives, 25. Traditionally there were 18 types of bananas and there were 4 additional banana names. There were four banana metaphors found in the Balinese language; (3) the dynamics of the banana lexicon in Balinese from generation to generation showed a decrease. This was evidenced by the increase in answer D= Do not know or do not know at all from the older generation to adults and young group, for the name of banana, the banana category, and the understanding of the banana metaphor in Balinese.

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